

FOR IMMEDIATE RELEASE

Europe's leading health innovators gather to confront biggest challenges in paediatric health data

Barcelona, April 9, 2026

More than 50 clinicians, data scientists, digital health innovators and industry leaders gathered in Barcelona to participate in an international hackathon to develop a financially sustainable model to support federated data sharing between European children's hospitals.

Why paediatric data sharing matters

Strong regulations exist to safeguard patient data and privacy. While important and necessary, these protections can make it challenging for hospitals and researchers to conduct research and develop new treatments.

In paediatrics and rare diseases, patient populations are often small. This means clinicians and researchers may not have access to enough data to support faster research, evaluate new treatments or improve services. Without broader, comparable data, health systems can also struggle to make the best use of limited resources.

Finding new ways to collaborate across borders is essential to improving outcomes for children and young people.

Building a Paediatric Health Data Space

The PHEMS Project, funded by Horizon Europe and UKRI, is building a Paediatric Health Data Space (PHDS) to address the data needs in paediatrics. The PHDS will allow participating hospitals to share data in a federated network while maintaining full control over their data and preserving patient privacy. Federated data sharing means organisations can learn from each other's data without actually moving or pooling the data itself, by securely analysing it where it already sits and only sharing the results.

Exploring Long-term sustainability

The PHEMS Business Hackathon focused on one key question: how can a system like the Paediatric Health Data Space be sustained over the long term?

Bringing together experts from hospitals, research organizations, the pharmaceutical industry and innovation ecosystems, the PHEMS Business Hackathon was a collaborative forum to explore exploitation models and long-term sustainability strategies for the PHDS. Through interactive workshops, participants co-created a range of models to help sustain paediatric data sharing in Europe. The Hackathon also reinforced a growing Europe-wide commitment to unlocking the potential of paediatric health data.

Pekka Kahri, the PHEMS project coordinator said:

"The hackathon validated that there is both demand and willingness to pay for analytical studies, scientific research, clinical trials, and innovation in paediatrics. This is a major landmark in our journey towards a sustainable economic model for PHDS."

A full analysis of the hackathon results will be published in June 2026.

ENDS

NOTES TO EDITORS

About the PHEMS Project

The PHEMS Consortium consists of six leading European paediatric hospitals from the European Children's Hospital Organization (ECHO) community and of leading-edge technical partners.

The consortium hospital partners are HUS Helsinki University Hospital (Finland), Erasmus University Medical Center Rotterdam (Netherlands), Meyer Children's Hospital IRCCS in Florence (Italy), SJD Barcelona Children's Hospital and SJD Research Foundation (Spain), Great Ormond Street Hospital for Children in London and University College London (United Kingdom), Children's Clinical University Hospital in Riga (Latvia). In addition to Childrens' Hospitals, the PHEMS consortium includes technology partners: Tieto (Finland), Aridhia Informatics Limited (UK) and VEIL.AI (Finland) and two professional services partners: The Hyve B.V. (Netherlands) and GENESIS Biomed (Spain).

For more information visit <https://phems.eu/> or contact

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Hackathon Participants at the Barcelona Health Hub, Barcelona, Spain

Hackathon participants during workshop at the Barcelona Health Hub, Barcelona, Spain